

From Optimal to Actionable: Reconciling Spatial Process Heterogeneity with Administrative Boundaries via Regularised Spatial Regimes Learner (RSRL)

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GISRUK 2026

Summary

Misalignment between spatial process heterogeneity and administrative boundaries is a long-standing issue in place-based decision-making. This often makes it challenging to translate results from data-driven spatial process modelling into direct evidence for place-based interventions. Based on the idea of endogenous spatial regimes, this paper proposed a Regularised Spatial Regimes Learner (RSRL), which allows decision-makers to explicitly trade off model performance against administrative burden. RSRL employs two regularisation parameters, α and λ , to respectively constrain the model search space and bias the pruning process toward cross-boundary edges. A real-world example on modelling spatial inequalities in self-rated health in Greater Manchester health region was used to demonstrate the usefulness of RSRL.

KEYWORDS: Spatial regimes, Spatial process heterogeneity, Administrative boundary, Regularisation, SKATER

1 Introduction

Boundary misalignment is a primary source of cross-boundary issues and remains a persistent concern in place-based policy making and governance. One of their root causes lies in a structural misalignment: spatial processes vary continuously and diffusively as human–environment interaction systems are inherently holistic and dynamic, whereas governance and institutional arrangements almost necessarily depend on discrete, static, and administratively defined boundaries (Barca, 2009). This deep-rooted challenge helps explain why, despite growing methodological advances in revealing and measuring underlying spatial process heterogeneity, such evidence remains limited in its adoption within evidence-based practice (Fotheringham et al., 2025). As a result, in practice, exogenously defined discrete spatial regimes and multilevel models are often preferred, even though it

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may compromise context responsiveness due to misspecification while data-driven spatially varying coefficient (SVC) models can recover underlying spatial varying processes much more accurately (Card and Krueger, 1993; Chay and Greenstone, 2003; Banerjee et al., 2020).

In recent work, Anselin and Amaral (2024) introduced an intermediate concept called endogenous spatial regimes. Within a data-driven framework, this method aims to solve the regimes and coefficients simultaneously, leveraging a heuristic that operates in a manner similar with SKATER (Spatial 'K'luster Analysis by Tree Edge Removal, Assunção et al., 2006), but optimising the Residual Sum of Squares (RSS) for each subtree after edge removal (instead of dissimilarity) as the pruning criterion for the Minimum spanning tree (MST). By identifying multivariate discrete heterogeneity in spatial processes, it is more suitable than conventional SVCs for supporting place-based interventions, which typically require space to be segmented into a finite number of spatially contiguous subsets with clear boundaries (Barca et al., 2012). Nevertheless, the delineated spatial regimes are often irregular in shape or ambiguous in interpretation, which still limits their practical applicability.

To address this issue, this paper proposed Regularised Spatial Regimes Learner (RSRL), two boundary-aware regularisation parameters, α and λ , was introduced and embedded within endogenous spatial regimes heuristics, allowing both the model search space and the pruning criterion to be adjusted in a principled manner. This design can help reconcile spatial process heterogeneity with predefined boundaries. An empirical application on the determinants of self-rated health conditions in the Greater Manchester health region¹, England, was used for demonstration.

2 Regularised Spatial Regimes Learner

A spatial regimes linear regression can be specified as:

$$y = \mathbf{Z}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \epsilon \tag{1}$$

where

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}_1 & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{X}_2 & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{X}_J \end{bmatrix}, \boldsymbol{\beta} = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \\ \vdots \\ \beta_J \end{bmatrix}$$

with \mathbf{X}_j indicating the design matrix within regime j , $j = 1, \dots, J$ and β_j containing the coefficients for regime j . When identifying endogenous spatial regimes, both \mathbf{Z} and $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ can be produced by the heuristics described in Anselin and Amaral (2024). Models were selected based on the minimum corrected Akaike Information Criterion (AICc) in this paper.

¹Here, the Greater Manchester health region refers to all the 10 Clinical Commissioning Groups overlapping with it, see details at Section 3.1

2.1 α regularisation

In the aforementioned heuristics, the MST² is used to constrain the model search space, transforming the NP-hard graph partitioning problem into a more tractable tree-pruning task. Therefore, how edge weights can be defined in the spatial adjacency graph from which the MST is constructed, which are typically based on attribute based distances, has a substantial influence on how endogenous spatial regimes are delineated and interpreted. A regularisation parameter $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ is introduced here to allow controls.

Let $G = (V, E)$ denote the spatial adjacency graph, where $V = \{1, \dots, n\}$ indexes spatial units and $E \subset V \times V$ is the set of undirected edges. In RSRL, edge weights are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} w_{ij}^{(0)} &= d_{ij}, \\ \tilde{w}_{ij}(\alpha) &= w_{ij}^{(0)} + \alpha b \partial_{ij}, \quad (i, j) \in E, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $w_{ij}^{(0)}$ is the raw edge weights between adjacent units i and j , which are here defined as distances (d_{ij}) between residuals from linear regression so as to proxy the underlying multivariate spatial process, and

$$\partial_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & g_i \neq g_j \\ 0, & g_i = g_j \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

is the indicator function associated with exogenously defined groups $\{g_i\}$, such as administrative units, catchment areas, or ecological regions. The scaling factor

$$b = [\max\{d_{ij} : g_i = g_j\} - \min\{d_{ij} : g_i \neq g_j\}]_+, \quad (4)$$

with $[x]_+ = \max(x, 0)$, can offer an data-adaptive normalization of the penalty. α can be adjusted to control the trade-off between process smoothness and cross-boundary characterisation. When $\alpha = 0$, a standard attribute-based MST is generated. When $\alpha = 1$, subtrees are connected through cross-boundary edges only when necessary. The higher the α , the less likely cross-boundary edges are to be selected in the MST.

2.2 λ regularisation

Once a MST is constructed, the edge whose removal results in the greatest reduction in terms of RSS is selected for pruning. However, RSS is not a linear measure of model evidence. It is therefore transformed into a log-likelihood ratio, so that under a Gaussian error assumption it can be is equivalent to an additive difference in logarithmic model evidence:

²An minimum spanning tree (MST) is a subset of edges that connects all vertices in a spatial adjacency graph without forming cycles and with the minimum possible total edge weight.

$$\Delta\ell_{ij} = \frac{n}{2} \log \left(\frac{\text{RSS}(M_0)}{\text{RSS}(M_1^{ij})} \right), \quad (5)$$

where M_0 and M_1^{ij} represent models before and after removing edge (i, j) . Then, another regularisation parameter, $\lambda \in [0, 1]$, is introduced in RSRL to regulate the weight placed on cross-boundary evidence during the pruning stage:

$$\tilde{\Delta}\ell_{ij}(\lambda) = \Delta\ell_{ij} - \lambda \kappa (1 - \partial_{ij}), \quad (6)$$

where the scaling factor

$$\kappa = \max_{(i,j) \in E} \{\Delta\ell_{ij}\}, \quad (7)$$

is adaptively updated at each pruning step. λ can be interpreted as the degree to which cutting evidence can be traded off in order to avoid cross-boundary regimes. When $\lambda = 0$, pruning follows the standard SKATER-like criterion. When $\lambda = 1$, pruning is restricted to cross-boundary edges whenever feasible. Higher values of λ indicate a greater priority placed on evidence from cutting cross-boundary edges. When $\alpha=\lambda=0$, RSRL reduces to the model of Anselin and Amaral (2024).

3 Empirical Demonstration

3.1 Data and variables

A modelling application on spatial inequalities in self-rated health conditions in the Greater Manchester health region was used here for demonstration. In order to align with the National Health Services (NHS) catchment area, the Greater Manchester health region is defined as the spatial concatenation of the coverage of the NHS Greater Manchester Integrated Care Board and the NHS Tameside and Glossop Clinical Commissioning Group in this paper. The dependent variable is derived from the variable General Health of the UK 2021 Population Census³ and is measured by the percentage of residents who rate themselves as ‘4 - Bad health’ and ‘5 - Very bad health’ in each Lower layer Super Output Area (LSOA)⁴. The independent variables list includes six widely recognised determinants of health selected from the demographic, socio-economic and environmental perspectives respectively (Dahlgren and Whitehead, 2021): the percentage of older adults (PctOver65) and the percentage of whites (PctWhite) from the 2021 Census, the 2019 income and

³The General health variable is defined as a person’s assessment of the general state of their health, ranging from ‘1 - Very good health’ to ‘5 - Very bad health’ on a five-point ordinal scale. UK Census 2021 is available at <https://www.ons.gov.uk/census>.

⁴Lower layer Super Output Areas are the second-lowest level of geography for UK census statistics. They comprise between 400 and 1,200 households with a usual resident population of between 1,000 and 3,000.

crime deprivation index (IncomeScore and CrimeScore)⁵, as well as logarithmic median house prices (HousePrice)⁶ and the index of air quality (AirQuality)⁷. All the variables were standardised to ensure comparability.

3.2 Results

A global model was first fitted as a baseline for following local extensions. All independent variables showed highly significant associations with the percentage of people reporting bad or very bad health, and the directions of the estimated coefficients were consistent with existing findings (Table 1).

Table 1: Global model (OLS) results

Variable	Est.	SE	t value	Pr(> t)	
Intercept	0.000	0.012	0.000	1	
Pct65over	0.408	0.016	24.899	<2e-16	***
PctWhite	0.217	0.015	14.211	<2e-16	***
IncomeScore	0.922	0.019	49.707	<2e-16	***
CrimeScore	0.069	0.017	4.020	6.06e-05	***
HousePrice	-0.125	0.015	-8.121	8.73e-16	***
AirQuality	-0.071	0.014	-5.102	3.73e-07	***
N			1723		
R ²			0.760		
AICc			2447.517		

Local Authorities (LAD, 11 in total) were defined as the exogenous actionable administrative units. The above global model (OLS) and Spatial Regimes Model (SRM) were calibrated to represent place-neutral and LAD-specific specification. Four combinations of α and λ ($\alpha=\lambda=0$, $\alpha=1$ while $\lambda=0$, $\alpha=1$ while $\lambda=0.5$, and $\alpha=\lambda=1$) were selected to regularise the endogenous spatial regimes (Table 2). It can be observed that when $\alpha=\lambda=0$, which equivalent to endogenous spatial regimes, the model achieves the best performance (R² and AICc) among all the selected models. However, it also generates the largest number of new regime boundaries, substantially increasing administrative burden and almost unactionable. When $\alpha=1$ and $\lambda=0$, spatial regimes that do not overlap with administrative boundaries almost disappear. Although the number of regimes increases slightly, the

⁵The income deprivation index measures the percentage of the population in an area who are out-of-work or are in work but with low earnings. The crime deprivation index measures the risk of personal and material victimisation at local level. The data is available at <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/english-indices-of-deprivation-2019>.

⁶To mitigate the effect of pandemic on housing market, median house prices were averaged across four quarters in 2022, and missing data were imputed using the average from 2021 or average of first-order adjacent LSOAs. The data is available at <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/housing/datasets/medianpricepaidbylowerlayersuperoutputareahpsadatataset46>.

⁷The index of air quality was calculated from the inverse of Air Quality Domain score from the Access to Healthy Assets & Hazards (AHAH) version 3. The data is available at <https://data.geods.ac.uk/dataset/access-to-healthy-assets-hazards-ahah-previous-versions>.

overall delineation is constrained by administrative areas, making the delineation easier to interpret. When λ increases to 0.5, candidate delineations that do not follow administrative boundaries have to deliver at least double the evidence gain of boundary aligned cuts. The number of regimes is thereby substantially reduced to 11, with only 5 new regime boundaries introduced, markedly lowering the complexity of potential actions compared with the previous two models. When $\alpha=\lambda=1$, all regimes converge to local authority district boundaries. Compared with SRM, RSRL further identifies local areas that do not require differentiated interventions, such as Bolton and Bury, and Tameside and Glossop (part of the High Peak LAD), reflecting their shared spatial contexts: the former pair are both historically associated with the cotton textile industry, while the latter belong to the same Clinical Commissioning Group.

$\alpha = 0; \lambda = 0$

$\alpha = 1; \lambda = 0$

$\alpha = 1; \lambda = 0.5$

$\alpha = 1; \lambda = 1$

— Local authority — Spatial regimes

Figure 1: Spatial regime delineations from RSRL with different combinations of α and λ (each fill colour represents a delineated spatial regime; where boundaries of spatial regimes overlap with administrative boundaries, only the latter are shown)

Figure 1 illustrated distinct delineation patterns, and the analysis focused on the model that per-

Table 2: Comparison of models under different spatial regime delineations

Model	Regimes	Boundaries ¹	F _{Chow}	R ²	AICc
OLS	1	0	-	0.760	2447.517
SRM	11	0	4.1471***	0.796	2315.063
RSRL _{$\alpha=\lambda=0$}	34	84	5.6365***	0.872	1902.058
RSRL _{$\alpha=1, \lambda=0$}	36	47	4.9468***	0.868	1989.434
RSRL _{$\alpha=1, \lambda=0.5$}	11	5	6.0344***	0.809	2201.341
RSRL _{$\alpha=\lambda=1$}	9	0	4.8468***	0.794	2303.524

¹ Number of regime boundary pairs delineated by the model that do not fully overlapped with administrative boundaries.

formed best according to the Chow test (RSRL _{$\alpha=1, \lambda=0.5$}). Same as RSRL with $\alpha=\lambda=1$, Bolton and Bury are merged into a single regime, as are Tameside and Glossop. Another cross-boundary regime combines Rochdale, Oldham, and North Manchester (including Harpurhey, Moston, and Blackley), which share a strongly post-industrial, working-class and socioeconomically deprived context. By contrast, Trafford is grouped into the same regime as South Manchester (including Didsbury, Chorlton, and Withington), areas that are more affluent and shaped by professional employment. Manchester City Centre, the student communities around the University of Manchester (UoM) and the University of Salford (UoS), and the area around Manchester Airport are identified as within-boundary hyper-local regimes. This highlights the significance of finer-grained, community-level place-based policy making in a region such as Manchester, where local profiles are highly diverse.

4 Discussion

The excessive administrative burden and bureaucratic complexity arising from boundary misalignment can reduce local governments’ propensity when designing place-based interventions, even when supported by evidence. In response, decision-makers often gravitate toward administratively expedient ‘one-size-fits-all’ solutions (OECD, 2025). To address this tension, this paper developed a Regularised Spatial Regimes Learner (RSRL), which introduces two tunable regularisation parameters into endogenous spatial regimes to bridge purely exogenous and data-driven frameworks for delineating space based on spatial process heterogeneity, thereby providing an intermediate form of evidence. The core principle of RSRL is to minimise the number of decision regimes while maintaining context responsiveness, and that regime boundaries should align as closely as possible with administrative boundaries to facilitate implementation. The regularisation parameters α and λ are interpretable in a policy context. As their values increase, extremely fragmented regimes are reduced, giving way to delineations that either partially align with administrative boundaries or hyper-local but supported by strong evidence, and finally converge to individual administrative units or their unions, helping to mitigate policy fragmentation and cross-boundary issues. This paper is limited to linear specifications of spatial regimes, the usefulness of RSRL in more complex tasks will be investigated in future work.

5 Biography

Sui Zhang is a third year PhD student in Planning and Environmental Management at the University of Manchester. His research interests mainly include spatially explicit methodological development and spatial inequalities in health.

References

- Anselin, L. & Amaral, P. (2024). Endogenous spatial regimes. *Journal of Geographical Systems*, 26(2), 209–234, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10109-023-00411-2>.
- Assunção, R. M., Neves, M. C., Câmara, G., & Da Costa Freitas, C. (2006). Efficient regionalization techniques for socio-economic geographical units using minimum spanning trees. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 20(7), 797–811, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658810600665111>.
- Banerjee, A., Duflo, E., & Qian, N. (2020). On the road: Access to transportation infrastructure and economic growth in china. *Journal of Development Economics*, 145, 102442, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdeveco.2020.102442>.
- Barca, F. (2009). *An agenda for a reformed cohesion policy: A place-based approach to meeting European challenges and expectations*. Eeri research paper series, Economics and Econometrics Research Institute (EERI), Brussels.
- Barca, F., McCann, P., & Rodríguez-Pose, A. (2012). The case for regional development intervention: Place-based versus place-neutral approaches. *Journal of Regional Science*, 52(1), 134–152, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9787.2011.00756.x>.
- Card, D. & Krueger, A. B. (1993). Minimum wages and employment: A case study of the fast food industry in new jersey and pennsylvania. *National Bureau of Economic Research Working Paper Series, No. 4509*, <https://doi.org/10.3386/w4509>.
- Chay, K. Y. & Greenstone, M. (2003). The impact of air pollution on infant mortality: Evidence from geographic variation in pollution shocks induced by a recession*. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 118(3), 1121–1167, <https://doi.org/10.1162/00335530360698513>.
- Dahlgren, G. & Whitehead, M. (2021). The dahlgren-whitehead model of health determinants: 30 years on and still chasing rainbows. *Public Health*, 199, 20–24, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2021.08.009>.
- Fotheringham, A. S., et al. (2025). Exploring Spatial Context: A Comprehensive Bibliography of GWR and MGWR. *arXiv e-prints*, (pp. arXiv:2404.16209)., arXiv:2404.16209, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2404.16209>.
- OECD (2025). *Place-Based Policies for the Future*. Oecd regional development studies, OECD Publishing, Paris.